

Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) for Smart Factories: Enabling Technologies and Challenges in Industry 4.0

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Abstract—With the recent advance of technologies, smart factories are no longer just the subjects of science fiction and are now becoming a reality [1]. It is essential for a smart factory builder to understand the different technologies and the challenges in industry 4.0. Many researches show the potential of Integrated Sensing And Communication (ISAC) in smart factories, including understanding the employees, gesture commands and monitoring the equipment, processes [1]. In this paper, we will investigation in the key technologies for ISAC and their application in Industry 4.0. Before the conclusion of this paper, we will discuss about the challenges and future directions for ISAC in industry 4.0

Index Terms—ISAC, Industry 4.0, Automation, IoT, IIoT, Internet of Things, Smart Factories

I. INTRODUCTION

The fourth industrial revolution, commonly known as Industry 4.0, is transforming traditional manufacturing processes by integrating advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, and cyber-physical systems. This convergence of physical and digital domains aims to enhance automation, improve operational efficiency, and enable real-time decision-making in smart factories as explained in Figure 2. As these systems become increasingly interconnected, the demand for seamless and efficient communication and sensing solutions has grown significantly .

In this context, Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) has emerged as a promising paradigm to address the dual needs of communication and environmental awareness in Industry 4.0. Unlike traditional systems where communication and sensing operate independently, ISAC unifies these functions within a single infrastructure. This integration allows for the simultaneous transmission of data and acquisition of critical sensing information, leading to more efficient resource utilization, reduced hardware complexity, and enhanced performance.

Fig. 1. ISAC IN SMART FACTORIES

ISAC in Industry 4.0 can be applied to various use cases, such as:

- Autonomous Robots and Drones: Enabling precise localization, navigation, and data communication.
- Predictive Maintenance: Utilizing sensor data to monitor the health of machines and predict potential failures.
- Real-time Localization and Tracking: Enhancing operational efficiency by accurately tracking assets and workers within a factory.
- High-speed Communication for IIoT: Facilitating reliable and low-latency data exchange between interconnected devices.

However, the integration of sensing and communication poses several challenges. For instance, balancing the trade-off between communication capacity and sensing accuracy, mitigating interference between the two functions, and ensuring low latency and high reliability are critical considerations in industrial environments.

This paper presents a comprehensive overview of ISAC for Industry 4.0, focusing on its enabling technologies, system architecture, and potential applications in smart factories. We analyze the associated challenges, and provide solutions to address these issues. Furthermore, we discuss the future prospects of ISAC, including its integration with emerging technologies such as 6G networks, edge computing, and digital twins, to further enhance the capabilities of Industry 4.0 as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 2. Smart Factories communication

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

The convergence of sensing and communication has gained significant attention in the context of next-generation wireless systems, particularly in Industry 4.0. The concept of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) aims to unify the traditionally separate functions of environmental sensing and data communication into a single system, leveraging shared hardware, spectrum, and computational resources [2].

A. Evolution of ISAC

In traditional wireless systems, sensing and communication operate independently, leading to redundant infrastructure, suboptimal resource utilization, and increased costs. ISAC addresses these challenges by integrating both functionalities, enabling smart factories to simultaneously monitor their environment and exchange data using a unified platform [2] [3]. This integration is particularly relevant in the context of Industry 4.0, where real-time data acquisition and high-speed communication are critical for automation, predictive maintenance, and resource optimization.

Key Characteristics of ISAC:

- **Joint Resource Utilization:** ISAC systems share resources across time, frequency, and space domains, significantly enhancing spectral efficiency.
- **Simultaneous Sensing and Communication:** A single waveform can perform both sensing and communication, reducing hardware complexity and enabling more compact and cost-effective designs [2] [4].

B. Application Domains of ISAC

ISAC technology finds applications in various domains relevant to Industry 4.0:

- 1) **High-Accuracy Localization and Tracking:** ISAC enables precise tracking of assets and workers within factories, enhancing operational efficiency and safety. Use cases include autonomous robots navigating factory floors and drones conducting inventory management [2].
- 2) **Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM):** ISAC systems can perform real-time mapping and localization using radio frequency (RF) signals, offering significant advantages over traditional SLAM techniques that rely on separate sensors [2].
- 3) **Predictive Maintenance and Monitoring:** By integrating sensing capabilities into communication devices, ISAC allows continuous monitoring of machinery and infrastructure, enabling predictive maintenance and reducing downtime [1].

- 4) **Collaborative Robotics:** ISAC supports the seamless operation of collaborative robots (cobots) that require real-time communication and environmental sensing to interact safely with human workers [4].

C. Enabling Technologies for ISAC in Industry 4.0

The successful implementation of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) in Industry 4.0 relies on a set of advanced enabling technologies. These technologies address the challenges of resource efficiency, latency, accuracy, and scalability, which are critical for smart factory operations. Below, we elaborate on five key technologies: OFDM and MIMO, Beamforming, Machine Learning (ML), 6G Networks, and Edge Computing.

- **OFDM and MIMO:** OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing) provides high spectral efficiency and robustness against multipath fading, making it a popular choice for ISAC waveform design. MIMO (Multiple-Input Multiple-Output) enhances spatial diversity, enabling high-capacity communication and accurate sensing [3].
- **Beamforming and Hybrid Beamforming:** Beamforming directs signals towards specific targets, improving sensing accuracy and communication reliability. Hybrid beamforming, which combines analog and digital techniques, is particularly useful for large antenna arrays in ISAC systems [3] [4].
- **Machine Learning (ML):** ML algorithms optimize resource allocation, interference management, and anomaly detection, enhancing the performance of ISAC systems in dynamic industrial environments [3].
- **6G Networks:** The emerging 6G networks, with their ultra-low latency and massive connectivity, are expected to provide a robust infrastructure for ISAC in Industry 4.0. 6G will facilitate real-time control and high-speed data exchange between sensing and communication devices [2].

III. CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

A. Challenges in ISAC Implementation

Despite its potential, the integration of sensing and communication poses several challenges.

- **Joint Waveform Design:** Designing waveforms that optimize both communication and sensing performance is a complex task. Trade-offs must be managed between spectral efficiency, sensing accuracy, and communication reliability [3].
- **Interference Management:** In dense industrial environments, interference between sensing and communication functions can degrade system performance. Advanced signal processing and resource allocation techniques are required to mitigate this issue [3] [4].
- **Hardware Complexity:** Sharing hardware components between sensing and communication increases system complexity. Efficient hardware architectures are needed to minimize power consumption and cost [2].

- **Latency or Real-Time Requirements in Factories:** Many industrial processes require real-time feedback to control machinery, robots, and production lines. Autonomous robots and collaborative robots (cobots) operating near human workers must respond instantly to avoid accidents. For example, applications like precision assembly, quality control, and predictive maintenance rely on immediate data collection and processing to make accurate adjustments.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Many IIoT sensors, actuators, and communication nodes are deployed in remote or hard-to-reach areas where frequent battery replacement is impractical or costly. Transmitting large volumes of data in real-time requires significant power, especially in high-bandwidth environments like smart factories.

B. Related Work

Several research efforts have explored the joint design of sensing and communication systems:

- **Waveform Design:** Studies have proposed various ISAC waveform designs, including OFDM, FMCW (Frequency-Modulated Continuous Wave), and emerging waveforms like CAESAR (Carrier Agile Phased Array Radar) and FH-MIMO (Frequency-Hopping MIMO) [3] [1].
- **Radar-Aided Communication:** Research has demonstrated the use of radar systems to assist in communication tasks such as channel estimation and beam alignment, highlighting the synergy between sensing and communication [4].
- **Collaborative ISAC Systems:** Collaborative ISAC systems leverage multiple nodes to perform joint sensing and communication tasks, enhancing system resilience and coverage in industrial environments [4]

C. Proposed Solutions to ISAC Challenges in Industry 4.0

The integration of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) in Industry 4.0 offers numerous benefits but also presents critical challenges related to hardware complexity, interference management, latency, and energy efficiency. Table I goes directly to the potential solutions to address these challenges.

Hardware Complexity: Merging Radar and Communication Functionalities Challenge: Integrating sensing (e.g., radar) and communication functionalities into a single hardware platform increases design complexity, power consumption, and cost.

Solutions:

- **Software-Defined Radios (SDRs):** Use SDRs that allow dynamic reconfiguration of hardware for both sensing and communication tasks. This reduces the need for separate hardware modules and enhances flexibility.
- **Joint Waveform Design:** Design unified waveforms that can perform both communication and sensing functions, reducing the need for separate transmitters and receivers.

- **Hybrid Beamforming:** Implement hybrid beamforming techniques that share the same antenna array for both radar and communication, minimizing hardware redundancy while optimizing performance
- **Multi-Functional Antennas:** Develop antennas that can simultaneously handle communication and sensing signals, reducing the overall size and complexity of the system.

Interference: Balancing Sensing and Communication Resources

Challenge: Sensing and communication functions operating simultaneously can cause interference, leading to degraded performance for both tasks.

Solutions:

- **Dynamic Resource Allocation:** Implement adaptive resource allocation algorithms that dynamically distribute time, frequency, and power resources between sensing and communication based on real-time requirements.
- **Beamforming and Spatial Filtering:** Use beamforming to direct communication and sensing signals towards specific targets, minimizing interference. Spatial filtering can further suppress unwanted signals from other directions.
- **Interference-Aware Waveform Design:** Design waveforms that are robust to interference or can separate sensing and communication signals in the frequency domain.
- **Multi-User MIMO (MU-MIMO):** Employ MU-MIMO techniques to handle multiple sensing and communication tasks simultaneously, reducing mutual interference by spatially separating the signals.

Latency: Real-Time Requirements in Factories

Challenge: Smart factories require ultra-low latency to ensure real-time control, decision-making, and safety-critical operations.

Solutions:

- **6G Networks:** Leverage emerging 6G networks, which are designed to achieve latencies below 1 millisecond, providing ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC).
- **Edge Computing:** Deploy edge computing nodes close to the data sources to process data locally, reducing the need for long-distance communication and minimizing latency.
- **Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN):** Use TSN protocols that prioritize critical data flows and guarantee deterministic latency for time-sensitive industrial applications.
- **Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) Acceleration:** Implement hardware acceleration for FFT/IFFT operations, which are critical for OFDM-based ISAC systems, to reduce processing delays.

Energy Efficiency: Prolonging Battery Life for IIoT Devices Challenge: IIoT devices deployed in industrial environments often operate on limited battery power, requiring energy-efficient solutions to extend their operational life.

Solutions:

- **Energy-Efficient Waveforms:** Design waveforms with low peak-to-average power ratios (PAPR) to reduce power consumption during transmission.

- **Sleep and Wake Scheduling:** Implement duty-cycling mechanisms that allow devices to enter low-power sleep modes when not actively sensing or communicating, waking up only when necessary.
- **Energy Harvesting:** Incorporate energy harvesting technologies, such as solar, vibration, or RF energy harvesting, to supplement battery power and reduce reliance on external power sources.
- **Machine Learning for Power Management:** Use machine learning algorithms to predict network conditions and optimize power consumption dynamically based on workload and environmental factors.
- **Low-Power Communication Protocols:** Employ low-power wide-area network (LPWAN) protocols such as LoRaWAN or NB-IoT for non-time-critical communication tasks, minimizing energy consumption.

TABLE I

SUMMARY OF SOLUTIONS FOR ISAC CHALLENGES IN INDUSTRY 4.0

Challenge	Solutions
Hardware Complexity	Software-Defined Radios (SDRs), Joint Waveform Design, Hybrid Beamforming, Multi-Functional Antennas
Interference	Dynamic Resource Allocation, Beamforming and Spatial Filtering, Interference-Aware Waveform Design, Multi-User MIMO (MU-MIMO)
Latency	6G Networks, Edge Computing, Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), FFT Acceleration
Energy Efficiency	Energy-Efficient Waveforms, Sleep and Wake Scheduling, Energy Harvesting, Machine Learning for Power Management, Low-Power Communication Protocols

IV. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The integration of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) into Industry 4.0 holds immense potential to revolutionize industrial processes. However, several areas of development must be explored to unlock its full potential.

A. Integration of ISAC with Digital twins for real-time monitoring

Digital twins are virtual representations of physical assets, processes, or systems that are continuously updated with real-time data. The integration of ISAC with digital twins can enable real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimization of factory operations.

- **Real-Time Data Acquisition:** ISAC systems can provide continuous sensing and communication data to update digital twin models in real-time.
- **Predictive Maintenance:** By combining ISAC data with digital twins, factories can predict equipment failures, optimize maintenance schedules, and reduce downtime.
- **Process Optimization:** Digital twins powered by ISAC can simulate various scenarios to optimize production lines and resource allocation.

Impact: This integration will enhance situational awareness, operational efficiency, and decision-making in smart factories.

B. Integration of ISAC with 6G networks for ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC)

The upcoming **6G networks** promise to deliver ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC), massive connectivity, and unprecedented data rates. Integrating ISAC with 6G networks will significantly enhance industrial communication and sensing capabilities

- **Ultra-Low Latency:** 6G networks can reduce latency to sub-millisecond levels, enabling real-time control and automation in industrial processes.
- **High Reliability:** Enhanced reliability ensures seamless communication and sensing in critical applications, such as autonomous robots and collaborative robots (cobots).
- **Massive Connectivity:** 6G will support a massive number of connected devices, making it ideal for large-scale industrial environments.

Impact: The integration of ISAC with 6G will enable real-time, reliable, and scalable industrial operations, supporting advanced use cases like autonomous vehicles, remote control, and augmented reality (AR).

C. Integration of ISAC with AI-driven factory systems for enhanced decision-making

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly being used in Industry 4.0 to automate processes, optimize resource allocation, and enhance decision-making. The integration of ISAC with AI-driven factory systems can unlock new levels of automation and intelligence.

- **Data-Driven Insights:** ISAC systems provide rich sensing data that AI algorithms can analyze to derive actionable insights.
- **Anomaly Detection:** AI models can use ISAC data to detect anomalies in real-time, improving safety and reducing operational risks.
- **Intelligent Resource Management:** AI can dynamically allocate resources between sensing and communication tasks based on real-time demands.

Impact: This integration will lead to smarter, more autonomous factories capable of optimizing their operations with minimal human intervention.

D. Standardization of ISAC for industrial use

Despite its potential, ISAC lacks standardized frameworks, protocols, and interfaces for industrial deployment. Standardization is critical to ensure interoperability, reliability, and widespread adoption.

- **Unified Communication and Sensing Standards:** Establishing standards for joint waveform design, resource allocation, and interference management.
- **Industry-Specific Protocols:** Developing protocols tailored to different industrial sectors, such as manufacturing, logistics, and energy.

- **Regulatory Compliance:** Ensuring ISAC systems comply with regulatory requirements for safety, reliability, and data security.

Impact: Standardization will facilitate the widespread adoption of ISAC in various industries, ensuring compatibility and interoperability across different devices and systems.

E. Scalability to large factories

Scaling ISAC systems to large industrial environments presents unique challenges, such as managing a vast number of devices, minimizing interference, and ensuring efficient resource utilization.

- **Distributed ISAC Systems:** Deploying distributed ISAC nodes across large factories to ensure coverage, reduce latency, and enhance scalability.
- **Hierarchical Resource Management:** Implementing hierarchical resource management frameworks to efficiently allocate resources across different factory zones and devices.
- **Edge-Cloud Integration:** Combining edge computing for real-time local processing with cloud computing for centralized data analysis and long-term storage.

Impact: Scalable ISAC systems will enable seamless operation in large factories, supporting diverse applications ranging from asset tracking to autonomous mobile robots.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have explored the transformative potential of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) in the context of Industry 4.0. ISAC offers a unified framework that enables smart factories to simultaneously perform communication and environmental sensing, leading to more efficient resource utilization, reduced hardware complexity, and enhanced operational performance.

We highlighted the key enabling technologies, including OFDM, MIMO, beamforming, machine learning, and edge computing, which facilitate the seamless integration of ISAC in industrial environments. Furthermore, we discussed the critical challenges associated with ISAC deployment, such as hardware complexity, interference management, latency, and energy efficiency, and proposed solutions to address these issues.

Looking forward, the future of ISAC in Industry 4.0 lies in its integration with emerging technologies like digital twins, 6G networks, and AI-driven factory systems. Standardization and scalability will play a pivotal role in ensuring widespread adoption and interoperability across diverse industrial applications. By addressing these challenges and leveraging the proposed solutions, ISAC has the potential to revolutionize smart manufacturing, enabling real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and fully autonomous industrial operations.

As Industry 4.0 continues to evolve, ISAC will serve as a cornerstone technology, driving the next wave of innovation and enabling factories to operate with unprecedented levels of intelligence, efficiency, and flexibility.

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